

AFFILIATION MOTIVATION - AS A SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTOR FORMING THE VALUE SYSTEM OF YOUNG PEOPLE

Norkulova Nargiza Tashpulatovna¹, Galdiyeva Mehribon Durdiyevna², Askarova Nargiza Abdivaliyevna³,
Matyakubova Shoxista Odambov kizi⁴, Kurbanova Surayyo Tuynazar kizi⁵

¹Doctor (PhD) in psychological science, associate professor of "Psychology" department of applied science at Tashkent

²Doctor (PhD) in psychological sciences, acting associate professor of the Department of Psychology at the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences.

³Doctor (PhD) in psychological sciences, acting associate professor of the Department of Psychology at the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences.

⁴assistant at the Department of Psychology at the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences.

⁵assistant at the Department of Psychology at the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences.

nargiza.norkulova@mail.ru¹, mehribon.galdiyeva@gmail.com², nargizaasqarova111@gmail.com³

shohistamatyakubova55@gmail.com⁴, qurbonovasurayyo5@gmail.com⁵

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13383862>

Annotatsiya: The article analyzes the state of development of the affiliation motive among uzbek youth, in particular, the relationship of affiliation with the formation of youth value systems. Based on data from a psychological study and the opinion of foreign and domestic researchers, the author outlines the importance of developing this motivation among young people. The possibility of forming an affiliation motive is shown, which determines the further communicative success and professional competence of the younger generation

Kalit soʻzlar: affiliation motive, desire for acceptance, fear of rejection, social behavior, family values, reactive anxiety, personal anxiety.

1 INTRODUCTION

At the present stage, when the process of globalization is proceeding at an accelerated pace, the place and importance of information technology in human life, the need for effective organization of interpersonal relationships in society is increasingly increasing. As world practice shows, in recent years, an increase in the feeling of loneliness and unity in an individual has manifested itself as a negative phenomenon in society. According to the World Health Organization, more than 300 million people currently suffer from depression, resulting in 800,000 suicides among 15-29 year olds each year. There is a possibility of solving these problems at the level of national state programs of each republic; by 2022–2027, the number of countries will have their own national policies in accordance with the WHO Health 2027 program, increased from 58 to 92 percent¹. Currently, in the system of global higher education, the development of socio-psychological characteristics is of great importance as the effective formation in students of motives calling for educational and professional excellence, the development of social

activity and a sense of belonging among young people, improvement of the diagnostic system that studies the value system by studying the motive of affiliation, the development of motives in students calling for educational and professional excellence, the mitigation of psychological breakdowns that occur in them, the prevention of emotional stress states: loneliness, becoming a stranger, decadence, depression, the development of such socio-psychological features such as conative and integrative functions of the motive of affiliation, self-affirmation, desire for cooperation, communication [12].

Being loved and accepted is important for every member of a healthy society. When we are not loved, emptiness and hostility appear [11]. Therefore, one of the most important aspects considered in psychology is the need for affiliation (from English to affiliate - to join, to join) [8], which is associated with the direct satisfaction of a person in love and in close relationships. According to the famous social psychologist D. Myers: "Close attachment to other human beings is the axis around which the life of the human individual revolves, from infancy to death. From these close attachments a person draws strength and everyday joys." [10].

In the newest psychological dictionary V. Shaparya gives the following interpretation of this motivation:

¹ Report of the WHO Regional Office for Europe (Budapest, Hungary, analysis of behavioral and cultural factors for health and health equity for 2022–2027) – // Electronic resource / Access mode: hartlg@who.int. (date of access: 04/16/2024)

“The affiliation motive is a person’s desire to be in the company of other people, contributes to a direct reduction in anxiety, mitigating the consequences of both physiological and psychological stress, as well as the characteristics accompanying affiliative interaction (components of affiliative interaction) are ease, trust, understanding and emotional appeal”[19, 8]. Blocking the motive of affiliation causes a feeling of loneliness, alienation, and generates frustration[9]. H. Murray described the motive (need) for affiliation as follows: “To make friends and experience affection. Enjoy other people and live with them. Collaborate and communicate with them. Be in love. Join groups” [20, p. 83; 3].

2 MATERIAL AND METODS

The experience of scientific and theoretical interpretation of the socio-psychological characteristics of the motive of affiliation in foreign and commonwealth countries shows that the range of interpersonal relationships on the topic was studied in the research works of A.Mehrabyan. He separates two structural components of the affiliation motive: the need for affiliation (liking, support in a conversation) and the fear of being rejected (the conversation is not established or remains informal). Based on these studies, the author separately mentions the need for unity, the desire to expand knowledge, communication and cooperation, and the establishment of partnerships as structural elements of the affiliation motive [7; 9]. A review of the literature on the topic showed that in foreign countries, scientific research on the motive of affiliation was carried out in socio-psychological, pedagogical-psychological, psychoanalytic, anthropoethnographic, sociological, philosophical directions (G.Murray, H.Heckhausen, A.Mehrabyan, Z.Freud, A.Maslow, D.Myers, D.McClelland, I.Kuznetsova, S.Yurkovskaya, N.Tvorogova)[20;18;9;10;11].

The research we have conducted to study the affiliation motive indicates that its severity and characteristics of affiliative behavior are largely determined by the leading style of interaction in the family in early childhood. Moreover, the role of family upbringing and interaction style influences the child’s very perception, which in turn determines the characteristics of interaction with other people in the future, leaves an imprint on all further relationships (the ability to express feelings, preferred style, degree of comfortable interaction). We decided to study the nature of social affiliation as a motive that plays an important role in the development of an active civic position among young people and the formation of personality value systems of future specialists.

Theoretical analyzes have shown that the main features, features and development criteria that make up the affiliation motive occur precisely in the system of interpersonal relations [13]. Due to the fact that the manifestation of the affiliation motive depends on the society to which the person belongs, the socio-economic views of the people living in it, team psychology, awareness of the processes of human relationships, correct conclusions, and its development. All this was studied from an empirical point of view and criteria for managing the social behavior of students were developed [14].

2.1. Literature analysis

Motivation, in particular, the problem of affiliation motivation, the psychological characteristics associated with this phenomenon were studied by foreign scientists G.Murray, H.Heckhausen, A. Mehrabyan, R.Cattell, Z.Freud, A.Maslow, D. McClelland, D.Myers, T.Watson, J.Born, E.Fromm, R. Frager, D.Fadiman, J.Allport, J.Atkinson, B.Buunk, W. McDaugal and scientists from the CIS countries L. Petrazhitsky, B.Ananiev, A.Leontiev, A.Orlov, K. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, S.Rubinshtein, S.Ilyin, M. Magomed-Eminov, L. Kovalev, A. Markova, T. Mathis, R.Nemov, I.Kuznetsova, M.Matyukhina, T .Stephanenko. The concept of “Affiliation orientation” was first introduced into social psychology by A. Mehrabyan and S. Kshesinsky².

The study of the motivational process associated with the circle of friends is one of the most difficult problems, and the ideas of G. Murray and N. Tvorogova about the concept of affiliation motive are taken as the basis for it; the role of need in relation to the emotional-trust connection, which is part of the structure of the affiliation motive, was studied in the works of J. Mazurkevich, E. Melibrud, K. Obukhovskiy. The use of factor analysis in measuring the affiliation motive was proposed by R. Cattell, according to his assumption, in relation to affiliation there is a motivational tendency, which he called sociability³.

In the works of domestic psychologists E. Goziev, G.Shoumarov, B.Kodirov, V.Tokareva, V. Karimova, N.Safaev, Sh.Barotov, B.Umarov, Z. Nishanova, A.Faizullaev and A.Zhabborov 4 the conditions for the

² Heckhausen X. Motivation and activity. In 2 volumes - M.: Science, 1986. - T.2. – pp. 303-307.

³ Tvorogova N. Psychology of management. Workshop. – M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2008. – P. 125-150.; Obukhovskiy K. Galaxy of needs. Psychology of human drives. – St. Petersburg: Rech, 2003.– 294 p.; McClelland D. Human motivation. – St. Petersburg: Peter, 2007. – 672 p.

4 Goziev E. Developmental psychology. T.: "Universitet", 1999. - 48 p.; Shoumarov G. Problems of psychological service in the

formation of the spiritual, moral, ideological, political, economic, and professional image of the individual were studied; the institutions, sources and mechanisms of socialization that influence human social behavior and the factors that harmonize behavior were analyzed in local conditions. Although scientists have come to certain conclusions within the scope of their research, the socio-psychological mechanisms and factors of the impact of the affiliation motive directly on the spiritual and moral character, value system and social behavior of student youth have not been comprehensively studied.

2.2. Methods

Study. To study the psychological characteristics of the manifestation of affiliation motivation, we conducted a series of psychological studies among students of five metropolitan universities in Tashkent and compared behavioral data of motivational content with value-orientation indicators. During the study, we used the results of a socio-psychological questionnaire, which gave us the opportunity to compare the subjective opinions of students with other data obtained by diagnostic methods, for example, data from the A. Mehrabyan test modified by M.Sh. Magomed-Eminova. The latter technique was intended to diagnose two generalized stable motivators included in the structure of affiliation motivation - the desire for acceptance (SA) and the fear of rejection (FR) [7].

The complex used methods to identify the motive for affiliation by Mary Edwards [17; 59-62], the MAS method (motivating a person to achieve a goal, the desire for gambling and the desire for social prestige) by M.Kubyshkina [7; 415-417], methodology "Diagnostics of social values of an individual [1; 49-52], scale for assessing the level of reactive and personal anxiety by

educational system of Uzbekistan // Psychological problems of increasing the effectiveness of education and upbringing in new type of secondary special educational institutions. - Tashkent, 1998. - B. 13-15.; Kadyrov B. Talented children and their selection methodology.-Tashkent, 1992.- B. 32-33.; Tokareva V. Lichnost is a sales model of the national training staff// Psychological problems of increasing the effectiveness of education and upbringing in new type of secondary special educational institutions.- Tashkent, 1998.-S. 21-22.; Karimova V. The relevance of social-behavior management in the conditions of global changes/Psychology of the 21st century: theory, practical perspectives//Proceedings of the international scientific and practical conference. - T.: "Classical music", 2013.-B.32-35.;Safayev N. Spirituality and national identity of the individual. Monograph. – Tashkent: Fan, 2004.– 211 p.; Barotov Sh. Social-psychological and scientific-practical foundations of psychological service organization in Uzbekistan: Psikh.fan.dok. ...dis. T.,–1997.; Umarov B. Pedagogical foundations of formation of independent thinking in students during spiritual-educational activity: Ped. science. name ... diss.– T.: BSU, 2005.– 140 p.; Nishonova Z. High school psychology. - Tashkent: TDPU, 2003. - 136 p.; Faizullaev A. Motivational self-regulation skills. - Tashkent: TGU, 1987. - S. 19-50.; Jabbarov A. Ethnic foundations of pedagogical technology. - Tashkent: Zarkalam, 2006. - 48 p.

Ch.D. Spielberger and Yu.L. Hanina [2; 32-34]. The study involved 285 respondents, 73 girls, 212 boys. The age category of respondents ranged from 18 to 32 years, the average age of the studied audience was 21 years.

3 ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

According to the results of A. Mehrabyan's method modified by M.Sh. Magomed-Eminova in Table 1 shows that the motivation of fear of rejection, compared to the value of the desire for acceptance, is more pronounced among students who came from rural areas ($p < 0.004$). That is, this category of guys is afraid of being rejected by the new society in which they find themselves. And this suggests that not only close emotional contact with loved ones, but also the need to feel like "an integral element of something," as Bleier noted, to feel unity, a sense of group, to be capable of emotional consonance with it played a major role [15]

Psychologist E. Melibruda believes that "interpersonal relationships are no less important to us than the air we breathe." This is confirmed by a number of psychological studies that show that the need for affiliation is formed exclusively in communication with surrounding people, communication with significant people is especially important. This is accomplished through unification in thoughts, feelings, and actions with a positively significant person.[9], [11], [18].

I would also like to note that the motive for striving for acceptance among students who come from villages is also higher than among urban students. We can associate this with the students' desire for self-affirmation and self-realization. After all, it has been proven that people who do not have support behind them, who have no one to rely on, are more stimulated to success and career growth than those young people who are provided with everything (Table 1).

Table 1: Comparative analysis of data on measuring the affiliation motive among students from urban and rural areas (according to the Mann-Whitney U test)

Indicators	Average ranks		U	P
	City (N=157)	Village (N=115)		
Striving for Acceptance	132,7	141,6	843	0,355
Fear of Rejection	122,9	150,4	696	0,004

Answers to the question: "Did your parents often leave you alone as a child?" helped us identify the level of affiliation. In children whose parents often left home

alone in childhood, the level of the affiliation motive is much lower than in those with whom their parents were close. The study showed that children who suffered from loneliness in childhood are unaffiliated (Table 2). It should be noted that it is the need for affiliation that helps a person successfully interact with others, enter into emotional and trusting communication, which is important not only for achieving better results in the team's activities and improving relationships between peers, but also for each participant in the process communication separately, since through communication a person has the opportunity to get to know himself more deeply and, as a result, be less lonely in our constantly changing world[9, c. 48].

Table 2: Statistical analysis of the relationship between the indicative data of Mary Edwards' methods and the question "Did your parents often leave you alone as a child" (according to the Mann-Whitney U test)

Indicators	Average ranks		U	P
	«Yes» (N=28)	«No» (N=87)		
Affiliation level	47,1	61,5	911,5	0,043

Such revealing data are also confirmed in studies conducted by foreign scientists. In their opinion, one of the conditions for the development of the affiliation motive is constant emotional contact between mother and baby, which includes, along with verbal means of communication, tactile sensations - caresses, kisses, hugs, which can satisfy the child's need for love at an early stage of development. In this regard, it is useful to turn to the approach of the American scientist B. White to raising children at an early stage of development: "Turn to your child as often as possible and respond to his cries as quickly as you can"; "Don't refuse to hold your baby for fear of spoiling him, and don't let him cry for too long" (White B., 1982). White believes that if parents quickly respond to a child's crying, then the child accumulates positive ideas; if they do not answer immediately, then the baby experiences an accumulation of negative emotions, which in their total influence create doubts in the child whether they love him or care about him [7]. Ethnocultural differences are interesting in this regard. M. Mead, describing the characteristics of the Arapesh (New Guinea), tries to understand how the personality of a good-natured, meek, receptive adult is gradually formed from an Arapesh baby. The researcher suggests that this is largely due to the "continuous, warm feeling of security" that the child experiences from the moment of birth. It is typical that during the first months of life the baby is never left alone. A child's cry is a tragedy that

should be avoided at all costs, and this attitude of adults persists throughout the child's subsequent life. The baby is carried a lot in his arms, he is given the breast as soon as he starts to cry, he is always close to some woman who will give him her breast if necessary (Mead M., 1988) [Ibid].

Confirmation of our research can be seen in the work of other researchers who have found that when children, for certain reasons, are deprived of emotional communication due to the indifference or even hostility of the environment, they lose the ability to make such contacts in the future. Lack of contact with adults, that is, lack of communication affects the mental development of the child and reduces resistance to disease. Confirmation of the importance of satisfying the needs for affiliation are cases of hospitalism - "the acquisition of our civilization," as well as the results of a number of original experimental studies (experiments by G. Harlow on monkeys, Tronic "with a straight face", studies by J. Bowlby, M. Ainsworth and others.)[16]. There is a widespread opinion among experts that in the case of a child's isolation lasting more than 5-6 months, the changes are usually irreversible (Spitz, 1956, Olechowicz 1957). It was found that it is possible to restore broken emotional ties during this period of time, but no more than four times, after which the child ceases to strive for contact.

Statistical analysis of answers to the question "Who do you mostly spend your free time with?" showed clear gender differences in responses (Table 3).

Table 3: Statistical analysis of gender differences in the relationship between the question "Who do you mostly spend your free time with?" (according to criterion χ^2)

	Guys		Girls		Total number	
	quantity	%	quantity	%	quantity	%
Classmates	15	16,5	5	16,1	20	16,4
Classmates, friends from the yard	23	25,3	2	6,5	25	20,5
Darling	3	3,3	2	6,5	5	4,1
Family	36	39,6	22	71,0	58	47,5
Others	14	15,4	0	0,0	14	11,5

Total quantity	91	100,0	31	100,0	122	100,0
-----------------------	-----------	--------------	-----------	--------------	------------	--------------

($\chi^2=14,1$; $p<0,01$)

Among girls, 71% spend their free time with their family, 16.1% with their classmates and 6.5% with their classmates and makhalla friends or with their loved one. Data suggests that girls are more affiliated and attached to their family members. But at the same time, it indicates that there is family control over girls from family members. Guys also have high results of 39.6% associated with spending their free time with their families, but this is not as high as for girls. In next place are 25.3% with classmates and mahalla friends, and then 16.5% with classmates, 15.4% with new acquaintances, and in last place 3.3% with their beloved girlfriend. The conclusion suggests itself that the guys maintain their relationships with long-time friends, their communication develops in long-term relationships. But at the same time, they strive to expand their circle of acquaintances with new friends and relationships. Maybe this is due to the fact that men in society have more freedom and are not limited in communication than girls. Since the motive of affiliation is directly related to interpersonal relationships among group members, we interconnected questions from the SPS (socio-psychological questionnaire) with the results of measuring social values in the group.

Results obtained using methods for studying social values and the question (SVE) “Who do you mostly spend your free time with?” showed that students who choose intellectual values spend their free time primarily with their family, then with classmates, discussing their subjects, next with new acquaintances, with their beloved, and finally with classmates and friends from the yard. The main point that I would like to draw attention to is the relationship between intellectual values and family values. That is, young people focused on family values pay more attention to the development of their intellectual qualities and abilities. Thus, the conclusion suggests itself that the development of spiritual values of young people is the painstaking work of teachers, family and society (Table 4).

Table 4: Statistical analysis of the relationship between the question “Who do you mostly spend your free time with?” “and methods for measuring social values (according to the Kruskal Wallis criterion)

Indicators	Average ranks					X _n - sq ua	P
	«classmate»,	«with beloved»,	«with family»,	«with friends»,	Others (N=1)		

	ate s» (N=18)	friends from the yard» (N=22)	ved» (N=4)	mi ly» (N=52)	4)	re	
Professional	61,81	45,48	72,13	56,01	56,50	4,04	0,401
Financial	60,89	60,45	67,13	51,54	52,18	2,60	0,628
Family	59,56	48,34	48,25	55,78	62,57	3,15	0,533
Social	63,11	47,50	54,13	53,12	67,54	4,75	0,313
Collective	65,69	44,86	32,38	56,71	61,21	6,96	0,138
Moral	56,69	46,93	30,00	62,06	50,36	6,76	0,149
Psychical	67,67	58,75	62,50	50,78	50,29	4,57	0,334
Intelligent	59,36	37,43	46,00	61,72	58,54	9,90	0,042

In the course of our research, we established a connection between family care and other criteria (Table 5).

Table 5: Statistical analysis of the relationship between the MAS methodology and the question “Did your parents often leave you alone as a child?” (using Student’s t test)

As can be seen from the results presented in Table 5, children who did not experience loneliness in childhood from their parents, in the future they turn out to be more confident in themselves, in their abilities, and their desire for competition is higher than among children whose parents often were left alone. We can explain this by a feeling of security, thanks to which a person draws strength, becomes more resistant to outside influences, develops faith in his own strength, etc.

4 CONCLUSIONS

As you know, a positive attitude towards the world, trust in it, experiencing it as a source of comfort and security allows a person to successfully realize himself; he develops the need for love, sympathy, positive evaluation, approval, and the need to expand the sphere of communication with people. Adult family members are ambivalently significant for the child due to the simultaneous demands, prohibitions and rewards applied to him. It is in acts of communication that the presentation of the so-called “inner world” of one person to another is carried out [11].

Thus, our research confirmed that a person needs stability in love and friendship. He feels the need for spiritual comfort, for trusting relationships. And close people, in the person of their own parents, are able to reduce concern about the problem or completely resolve it, increase the activity of the individual, that is, provide significant social support.

Knowledge about the positive significance of the formation of affiliation motivation in the early stages of ontogenesis will, it seems to us, make it possible in the future to ensure and improve the system of training qualified personnel if the following psychological and pedagogical conditions are implemented:

propaganda of knowledge in pedagogical institutions, the media (mass media) that the formation of the motive of affiliation in the younger generation should begin from infancy, and it is necessary to improve the family values themselves;

the formation of motivation for affiliation among young people in the learning process should be one of the tasks of the professional activities of teachers of schools, lyceums, colleges, as well as higher educational institutions;

the goals of forming these types of motivation should include providing students with positive motivational states, characterized by a focus on active interaction in the process of communicative activity, as well as ensuring a positive self-concept oriented towards success;

the formation of motivation by the teacher is important to carry out in unity with the self-

Indicators	«Yes» (n=29)		«No » (n=89)		t	p
	Avg. mean ing	Stand ard. deviat ion	Avg. mean ing	Stand ard. deviat ion.		
Striving for social prestige	18,97	3,87	18,53	4,06	0,51	0,61
Desire for competition (gambling)	6,69	3,33	8,45	3,14	-2,58	0,01
Striving to achieve a goal	19,34	3,84	19,70	4,29	-0,39	0,69

development of motivation by students by including them in the process of assessing their own mental states and the results of educational activities;

the formation of motivation involves the use of a complex of psychological and pedagogical means, socio-psychological, corporate trainings that have appropriate developmental capabilities and implement the patterns of development of the affiliation motive

REFERENCES

- [1] Batarshev A.V. Psychodiagnostics in management: A practical guide: Educational and practical manual. - M.: Delo, 2005 - p.49-52
- [2] Large encyclopedia of psychological tests. - Eksmo.: Moscow, 2006.- p.67-72
- [3] Buunk B. Affiliation and helping interactions within organizations: a critical analysis of the role of social support with regard to occupational stress. \ in Stroebe W., Hewstone M. European Review of Social Psychology, - Chichester: John Wiley, 1990, 1, p. 293-322.
- [4] Galdieva, M. (2023). A study of the criteria defining social-psychological characteristics affecting the education of elementary school students. Journal Pedagogiki and psychology and contemporary education, (I).
- [5] Galdieva, M. (2023). A study of the criteria defining social-psychological characteristics affecting the education of elementary school students. Journal Pedagogy and psychology and contemporary education, (I).
- [6] .Galdieva, M. D. (2022). Study of the factors influencing the national education of students. Modern education (Uzbekistan), (10 (119)), 57-65.
- [7] Ilyin E.P. Motivation and motives. – St. Petersburg. : Peter. 2011.- p.363-470

- [8] Karpenko L.A. Brief psychological dictionary / Under general. ed. A.V. Petrovsky, M.G. Yaroshevsky.- M.: Politizdat, 1985.- p.29
- [9] Kuznetsova I.V. Motive of affiliation in interpersonal relationships: Dis. cand. psychol. Science: 19.00.05 St. Petersburg, 2006. - p-48.
- [10] Myers D. Social psychology: Translated from English - St. Petersburg: Petersburg - 2004. - pp. 401-404
- [11] Myasishchev V.N. Personality and neuroses. - L.: LSU. -1960.- p.42
- [12] Norkulova N.T. Affiliation motive is a socio-psychological factor forming the spiritual image of students/ Psych. Ph.D. (PhD) ... diss. autoref. - T.: TDIU, 2017. - 49 p.
- [13] 13. Norkulova N.T. Psychology of affiliation motivation in youth spirituality/Monograph.-Tashkent, "Science and Technology", 2015.- 152 p.
- [14] Norkulova.N.T.Ethnopsychological characteristics of the family values forming the affiliation motive among Uzbekistan's young students // European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – Vol. 3, No. 3.– 2015.– pp.12-17.(19.00.00; № 2).
- [15] Norkulova N.T. Ethnopsychological features of valuable orientations in formation of motive of an affiliation among student's youth // Bulletin of integrative psychology. - Russia, 2016. – № 18. – C. 48-52.(19.00.00; № 2)
- [16] Human psychology from birth to death. 2007- p.124-129
- [17] Serova L.G. Personnel selection tests\ “Psychological workshop” series. – Rostov-n\D.: Phoenix, 2004- p.59-62
- [18] Heckhausen H. Motivation and activity, vol.1. SPb.: Peter - 2003.- 859 p.
- [19] Shapar V.B. The latest psychological dictionary \V.B. Shapar, V.E.Rossokha, O.V. Shapar; edited by V.B. Shaparya.- 3rd edition-Rostovn\D.: Phoenix, 2007.- p-43
- [20] Murrey H. A. Exploration in Personalaty. – N.Y.,1938